

**Matthew Reynolds,
Professor of English
and Comparative
Criticism, University
of Oxford**

Knowledge for everyone, everywhere - Matthew Reynolds

Everyone everywhere should have access to research, but they don't. Open access publishing removes barriers, democratising access to knowledge.

There are several reasons why Matthew Reynolds decided to publish his book open access, the main one being his strong belief in the democratisation of knowledge.

The constraints of traditional publishing

Professor of English and Comparative Criticism at the University of Oxford, Reynolds says traditional academic publishing tends to be undemocratic. It keeps knowledge in an enclosed space, where only a privileged few – individuals and institutions who can afford expensive academic books or subscription fees – can access it.

Reynolds also thinks that traditional academic publishing tends to perpetuate established disciplinary structures and styles of writing. While these do have value, they can also hold back fresh thinking and restrict readership.

Breaking down barriers

Reynolds wants to break free from the traditional constraints of academic silos to produce more diverse and creative research outputs.

Literature, for example, doesn't belong in just one language or one location, he says. Interactions between different languages are a fundamental part of literary writing, but too often, literature is compartmentalised into national stories – English literature in the English department and Italian literature in the Italian department.

This is not people's lived experience of literature.

Literature transcending borders

Reynolds' latest book is called *Prismatic Jane Eyre: Close-Reading a World Novel Across Languages*. Both the research and the open access costs for book were AHRC-funded. Many academics from around the world collaborated with him. He says literary interpretations are richer when different voices and perspectives are involved.

Reynolds explained:

“Charlotte Brontë's novel doesn't just exist in English. It's been translated more than 600 times into more than 68 languages. Reviewing all this work by translators and publishers in different locations is creative work. It's collaborative and creative, remaking and discovering new significances in new locations.”

Encouraging diversity of thinking and research

Publishing open access freed Reynolds from established publishing norms, enabling him to produce more experimental content, including digital interactive maps and verbal animations. He selected his publisher as it had a reputation for being innovative and were interested in the digital, interactive elements of the book.

Many of his co-authors are from different intellectual and linguistic traditions and use English in a variety of ways. It was important to him that they could write authentically, in a style that suited them, rather than having a prestige house style imposed on them. He wanted to move away from academic jargon and for lots of different languages and perspectives to be represented on the page.

Reynolds thinks this approach makes it easier to reach a more diverse audience, with different reference points and different experiences.

He explained:

“The work I do is about reaching people from different disciplinary silos. And my book is different from the traditional reading experience – I want people to explore it in ways that are interesting to them. I didn’t want it to be the sort of book that symbolises knowledge and configures readers as receivers of knowledge. I wanted it to be an interactive experience for them.”

Being an established academic, he was confident to be bold in his publishing decisions, but notes that if it had been his first book, it could have been a more challenging decision.

The benefit

The book was downloaded roughly 10,000 times in the first nine months, with 20% of those downloads coming from the Global South, which Reynolds is very pleased about. He said:

“ It seemed very necessary that what we wrote about be readily available to people in the Global South, in all the places where the book was translated, stopping the practice of academic work being extractive.

Reaching a wider, bigger audience has also boosted Reynolds’ profile, with him being asked to give lectures in the universities of Tunis, Shanghai Jiao Tong, Brown, Princeton, Dongguk (Seoul) and Lille, as well as Manchester, Leeds, East Anglia and Oxford Brookes. Had he not published open access, Reynolds think his book would not have generated the same level of interest and excitement.

New projects

Beyond this AHRC-funded project, Reynolds is working on other books. He is very keen to publish open access again, but says it is not always obvious how to achieve this. For one collaborative volume he has negotiated a Green open access agreement with a long-established publisher. However, another book may not be able to be published open access, as funding has not yet been secured to cover the costs.